

From laughing into singing in Nordoff-Robbins Music Therapy: a case study of Carol

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Abstract: This study presents excerpts of the music therapy process of Carol with specific focus on leading her laughing into singing. Carol participated in Nordoff-Robbins Music Therapy sessions, a music-centered approach that understands music as the primary agent of therapeutic transformation. Carol is a young lady who likes laughing. She was born with Angelman Syndrome and has global developmental delay. Because she was often laughing during sessions, the music therapist worked with her laughs as potentials for expressing and communicating. We detected four stages that led her laughs into singing, adapted from Nordoff and Robbins (2007): Influenced laughs, Laughing-singing, Singing-laughing and Expressive singing.

Keywords: Nordoff-Robbins Music Therapy. Communication Development. Case Study.

Da risada ao canto na Musicoterapia Nordoff-Robbins: um estudo do caso Carol

Resumo: Este estudo apresenta recortes do processo musicoterapêutico de Carol com foco específico na condução da sua risada ao canto. Carol foi atendida na abordagem Nordoff-Robbins de Musicoterapia, uma abordagem musicocentrada que vê a música como agente primário da transformação terapêutica. Carol é uma moça risonha que nasceu com Síndrome de Angelman, e por isso tem atraso global do desenvolvimento. Por ela estar sempre rindo, a musicoterapeuta trabalhou com suas risadas durante as sessões como potenciais para se expressar e se comunicar. Detectamos quatro estágios que conduziram sua risada ao canto, adaptados de Nordoff e Robbins (2007): Risadas influenciadas, Risadas-canto, Cantos-risada e Canto expressivo.

Palavras-chave: Musicoterapia Nordoff-Robbins. Desenvolvimento da Comunicação. Estudo de Caso.

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Introduction

Nordoff-Robbins Music Therapy is a music-centered approach, also known as Creative Music Therapy, developed by the composer and pianist Paul Nordoff (1909-1977) together with the special educator Clive Robbins (1927-2011). Their partnership began in 1959 at the Sunfield Children's Home, a British Anthroposophical residence for children with special needs, and lasted for approximately 16 years. Throughout this time, they worked together attending children with disabilities and teaching formal training in Nordoff-Robbins Music Therapy in Europe and the United States. Today, this specialized therapeutic approach is widely practiced by many certified Nordoff-Robbins practitioners around the world in different musical and clinical contexts with people of any age and any health condition (GUERRERO *et al*, 2016; MAHONEY, 2016).

Nordoff-Robbins proposes a unique way to musically engage clients and help them to relate, communicate, and integrate in the world through meaningful, emotional, shared and unique experiences in improvised music (NORDOFF; ROBBINS, 2007; GUERRERO *et al*, 2016). Nordoff-Robbins music therapists believe that every individual possesses a core musicality that is integral to their well-being, so musical processes are the primary agent of therapeutic changes (AIGEN, 2014; GUERRERO *et al*, 2016). In other words, the art of spontaneous musical creation supports creative healing processes (ROBBINS, 1998). That's why musical interventions are to be creative, intense, and spontaneously focused on the client's potential and on the here and now (AIGEN, 2005; GUERRERO *et al*, 2016; NORDOFF; ROBBINS, 2007).

Paul Nordoff and Clive Robbins studied their music therapy work through recording and session-by-session analyses in order to understand the details of the client's musical communication and levels of interaction (NORDOFF; ROBBINS, 2007; GUERRERO *et al*, 2016). They worked to hear all the clients sounds and view their movements as potential musical expressions that could be met and worked with musically, even if the child they worked with was non-verbal, anxious and withdrawn, and entered sessions crying. These experiences have significance as they help the child to go from crying into singing, thus, communicating more and establishing more human contact. According to the authors, there is a four-stage process they could see the child moving through:

[...] (1) tonally, rhythmically, or expressively influenced vocalization; (2) crying-singing - the child's more-or-less continuous crying begins to be shaped by the improvisation (3) singing-crying - the child begins intentionally to sing with her "crying voice" (4) non-crying self-expressive singing - vocal musical partnership beginning (NORDOFF; ROBBINS, 2007, p. 216).

This study presents excerpts⁵ from the music therapy process of Carol, who participated in Nordoff-Robbins Music Therapy from 2019 to 2022. Carol was seen in weekly individual sessions in *Centro de Musicalização Integrado* (Integrated Music Center) of *Universidade Federal de Minas Gerais* (Federal University of Minas Gerais). The music therapist was a Nordoff-Robbins Level 1 trainee, enrolled in the blended learning training at New York University's Nordoff-Robbins Center for Music Therapy, which offered off-site training. Her co-therapists were music therapy graduate students at Federal University of Minas Gerais.

Carol⁶ presents as a happy young lady who likes laughing. She also likes holding dolls and magazine pages, watching old TV shows for kids, and listening to music. It was due to her love for music that the family decided to take her to Music Therapy. She was born with Angelman Syndrome, and her laughing can be considered a characteristic of this genetic condition. Also because of Angelman Syndrome, she has severe developmental delays, with motor, communication, and cognitive challenges. She needs help for walking and communicating. She takes medications to prevent febrile seizures.

When Carol began music therapy, she was 19 years old. She wore diapers all the time and needed help for all daily living activities. She had almost no verbal communication, she did not utilize spoken language, although according to her mother she had spoken "mum" when she was a child. People around her struggled to understand what she wanted and to know how much Carol understood about what was happening around her.

In this study we will be sharing the unfolding process of therapy chronologically, from 2019 to 2022, as we examine the specifics of a key element of the work: how Carol moved from laughing to singing, as the music therapist listened to her laughs as music. Therefore, this study analyzes the first four years of Carol's music therapy process based

⁵ Playlist: https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLWA9xkhloiuUoBZMv1bG-e8_uCWc6d23e

⁶ Carol's family signed the consent form agreeing with the disclosure of the sessions and the first name in scientific publications.

on the four-stage leading crying into singing proposed by Nordoff and Robbins (2007), adapted for laughing into singing: Influenced laughs, Laughing-singing, Singing-laughing and Expressive singing.

1 Influenced laughs

In the first sessions, in 2019, Carol often threw the instruments on the floor and laughed a lot. She put her hands behind her back, as if she was saying she didn't want to play. She did these things in a teasing, playful way, probably testing the new therapeutic relationship. The music therapists saw those things as Carol's potential: she could choose what she wanted, and thus develop autonomy.

Since the first session, even when she was laughing and didn't want to play, her vocalizations and her body movements were musically influenced, related in tempo and in tune with the improvisation created by the therapist vocally and on the guitar. She probably didn't do it intentionally, as her vocal sounds and movements were evoked and fragmentary responses to music. Still, she could perceive and feel the music. It was seen as a potential for Carol's engagement in a shared music experience and communication in music. The music therapist intentionally improvised vocally, shaping her vocalizations to match the pitch and duration of Carol's laughing (Figure 1). This was a strong characteristic of Carol's first year of music therapy.

Figure 1: Vocal and harmonic improvisation sung and played by the music therapist to accompany Carol's "influenced laughs" (Session 01).

Still in the first year, in session 10, Carol interacted with the therapists in a tickling game. The notes of her laughing were generally fast, high, and around the tonic, in other words, influenced by the music. The music therapist improvised on the guitar and with her voice, rhythmically and melodically related to Carol's vocalizations (Figure 2), aiming to encourage her to continue vocalizing and, thus, to cultivate vocalizations as a potential for singing and communication.

Figure 2: Musical Theme named *Fazer uma cosquinha* (To do a tickling), sung and played by the therapist during Carol's "influenced laughs" (Session 10).

The way Carol laughed in session 10 was not always influenced by the improvisation. More than that, sometimes her laughs also started to show melodic

contour and rhythmic patterns shaped by the improvisation. Sometimes, the music therapist intentionally gave space when singing, and Carol laughed in the tempo, as if she was asking the music to continue. For example, when giving space in session 10, Carol sang a musical phrase at the beginning of the harmonic cycle, showing that she understood the structure of the improvisation (Figure 3). Therefore, she began to show her potential of going to the next stage: “laughing-singing”.

Figure 3: Variation of the Musical Theme *Fazer uma cosquinha* (To do a tickling) when Carol interacted vocally with the music improvisation, precisely tuned (Session 10).

By the end of the first year, Carol’s mother reported that she seemed more aware of what was going on around her, responded more to requests, and stopped using diapers at home. Quoting Nordoff and Robbins (2007), she was “moving out of the isolation, the bleakness, the frustration that her pathology and lack of development had imposed” (NORDOFF; ROBBINS, 2007, p. 17).

2 Laughing-singing

During most sessions of the second and the third year of Carol’s course of therapy, she continued laughing and her laughs were shaped by the music, as illustrated in the next two examples. Session 35 was a remote pre-recorded session during social isolation in 2020, due to the lockdown in response to the Covid-19 pandemic. Carol’s mother recorded her responses in music and sent them back to the music therapist. For this session the therapists had recorded a precomposed song based on a clinical theme developed in previous live sessions named *Tema do Bolo* (The Cake Theme)⁷.

Carol’s responses to this song were laughs directly related to the music (Figure 4), in the same tonality played by the music therapist, C major. Most of the time, during

⁷ The Cake Theme began to be developed in session 30 (a remote live session), when Carol showed the therapists a photo of a cake, and her caregiver (who was by her side in that session) told us that Carol loves to eat cakes.

the chorus of the song, she sang in the spaces created by the music therapists' singing, similar to a call and response, and sometimes Carol anticipated the note of the next chord. In the last verse, during the dominant chord (G7), she sang together with the music therapist and the co-therapist, not after, showing a probable different music response to this harmonic function. She ended her vocalizations on the 5th note of the tonic chord. Thus, in this session, she showed a clear sense of tonality, sense of phrase structure and sense of conclusion, as her laughing was shaped by the form of the improvisation. In other words, she was “laughing-singing” in this shared music experience.

The musical notation consists of two systems. Each system has a top staff for Carol and a bottom staff for the Therapist. The first system shows Carol's vocal line with two triplet notes and the Therapist's accompaniment with a triplet accompaniment. The chords are C and Am. The second system shows Carol's vocal line with two triplet notes and the Therapist's accompaniment with a triplet accompaniment. The chords are Dm, G, and C.

Figure 4: Chorus of the song *Tema do Bolo* (The Cake Theme), when Carol's laughs were shaped by the song the music therapist was singing (Session 35).

In this period of therapy, precomposed songs were very important for Carol and her family, as they listened together to them over and over again. Meeting Nordoff-Robbins philosophy (AIGEN, 2005), these songs repeated use at sessions and at home met Carol' developmental need for stability and meaning.

Another example of “laughing-singing” happened during session 64. This was a remote live session, still during social isolation, with Carol, her mother, the music

therapist, and co-therapists⁸. The music therapist played the guitar and sang a new improvised song: *O som do ovinho é tchi tchi tchi* (The sound of the egg shaker is *tchi tchi tchi*) while Carol and the co-therapists played the egg shakers. The music therapist sang and gave space to Carol's vocalizations. (Figure 5)

In Figure 5 we can notice that the therapist was playing chords and singing in E major tonality and Carol was “laughing-singing” in tune. Her vocalizations were related with the musical theme structure: pulse and phrasing, generally right after the therapist singing phrase. Her laughing was clearly shaped by improvisation.

♩ = 100

The figure displays three musical excerpts. Each excerpt consists of two staves: Carol's vocalizations on top and the therapist's accompaniment on the bottom. The key signature is E major (three sharps) for the first two excerpts and E major (two sharps) for the third. The time signature is 12/8. The tempo is marked as ♩ = 100. Chords are indicated below the therapist's staff.

Excerpt 1: Carol's staff shows vocalizations. Therapist's staff shows accompaniment with chords: B B/F#, A E, B B/F#, B B/F#.

Excerpt 2: Carol's staff shows vocalizations. Therapist's staff shows accompaniment with chords: B B/F#, A E, B B/F#.

Excerpt 3: Carol's staff shows vocalizations. Therapist's staff shows accompaniment with chords: F#7, G#m E, F#7, F#7.

Figure 5: Three excerpts of the improvised song *O som do ovinho é tchi tchi tchi* (The sound of the egg shaker is *tchi tchi tchi*), when Carol was “laughing-singing” in the music (Session 64).

⁸ The therapy team was enlarged during the pandemic in order to shelter 4 music therapy students as co-therapists, since Carol likes news and being around groups of people. As we planned, Carol accepted it very well.

During this part of the course of therapy, Carol's mother reported that she started gesturing to go to the restroom with her hand and to communicate yes and no with her head. Carol's responsiveness in sessions were also generalizing to how she was relating to others outside of the sessions. We could see a *continuum*, as claimed by Aigen (2014), between musical achievements and nonmusical achievements in the music therapy process.

3 Singing-laughing

Going one step further, Carol's vocalizations started to sound closer to singing, keeping her laughing voice, and keeping her tune and pulse directly related to the music's tonality and tempo. So her developing musicality motivated her to sustain her engagement with others. She enjoyed singing, had more ways to articulate herself through singing, and this led to her being more related to others outside of the sessions.

In the example of session 84, the music therapist intentionally brought a compound time signature (12/8) to the improvisation, aiming a deeper matching with the rhythmic patterns of Carol's laughs. The music therapist also established a minor cyclic harmonic base in the tonality of E minor (Em / C / D / Em), waited for Carol's vocalizations as a call, and vocalized back in response, matching with the rhythm, melodic contour, and the qualities of Carol's voice.

During this musical encounter there was significant rhythmic engagement, illustrating Carol's intention to actively participate in the music. Sometimes it seemed that Carol even waited for the music therapist vocal responses. Carol was singing with her laughing voice, that means she was "singing-laughing", developing more self expressiveness. In Figure 6, we can notice an example of call and response between Carol and the music therapist in the shared music experience.

Figure 6: A moment of music engagement with Carol's "singing-laughing" (Session 84).

Most of the time Carol sang with a laughing voice. By the end of this session, after the music therapist sang her name, she vocalized "aaah" (two notes) in a different way, more thoughtful and less silly (Figure 7). She showed a potential for her "expressive singing" as her next stage, as an opportunity for her to explore other emotions with her voice.

Figure 7: Carol sang "aaah" without laughing (Session 84).

After these period of sessions, Carol's mother reported that she started to respond more to requests and communicate better. At home, she started to say "mamãe"

(mom), “*bebê*” (baby) (it’s the nickname of her youngest sister) and to rehearse to say the phrase “*amo a mamãe*” (I love mom). Her vocal articulation of the words was not perfect, but her communication was getting more effective. As Ansdell (2014) explained, when music therapist and client can sustain an emotional-musical exchange that is understandable and enjoyable for the client, this may help him/her to integrate and incorporate this kind of engagement with other people in everyday life.

4 Expressive singing

When Carol started to sing beyond her laughing voice, she showed us her emerging and unfolding “expressive singing”. In the following example from session 89, she explored more vocal sounds, vowels, timbres and registers of her voice. She brought new moods to the session, as if she was sharing more of her inner world and willing to engage and sustain emotionally meaningful interaction with the therapist.

The music therapist set a new feel in the improvised music to match Carol’s new musical expressions, utilizing a more flexible tempo and less defined phrase structure. Together the therapist and Carol began a deep dialogue in the music. Different from the examples of “laughing-singing” (when Carol responded to the music therapist’s melodies) and “singing-laughing” (when the music therapist responded to Carol’s vocalizations), in this session they alternated who initiated the musical ideas (Figure 8).

The figure consists of two musical systems. The top system is in 6/8 time with a tempo marking of ♩ = 80. Carol's part (top staff) begins with a whole note rest, followed by a half note G4, a quarter note F#4, and a quarter note E4. The therapist's part (bottom staff) has a whole note rest, followed by a quarter note G4, a quarter note A4, a quarter note B4, and a quarter note C#5. Chords B7 and C#m are indicated. A 'rit.' marking is placed between the two staves. The bottom system is in 12/8 time with a tempo marking of ♩ = 63. Carol's part (top staff) has a whole note rest, followed by a half note G4, a quarter note A4, a quarter note B4, a quarter note C#5, a quarter note B4, a quarter note A4, and a quarter note G4. The therapist's part (bottom staff) has a whole note rest, followed by eighth notes G4, A4, B4, C#5, B4, A4, and G4. Chords E and A are indicated.

Figure 8: Examples of the musical dialogue between Carol and the music therapist, alternating who initiated the musical ideas and exploring new possibilities of Carol’s voice (Session 89).

During these musical exchanges in this part of the music therapy process, Carol explored her voice in different ways and developed her singing and expressiveness even more. Quoting Birnbaum (2014), “the relationship created in music can be seen as an intersubjective field, the shared space in which communication and growth can take place” (BIRNBAUM, 2014, p. 32).

5 Conclusion Thoughts

The sensitively, responsively created music responded directly to Carol’s musicality. When we reach the individual’s innate musical core in the improvised music making, we help her to discover her own strengths and to develop potentials to communicate musically (AIGEN, 2005; ANSDELL, 2014).

Carol was able to feel her laughs connecting in a new way with a surrounding, emotionally potent world. In line with Nordoff and Robbins, when she is heard and understood, not only can she discover “meaning, fulfillment, and pleasure in musicing” (NORDOFF; ROBBINS, 2007, p. 216), she can also realize her awakening strengths that make a creative journey of communication and human engagement possible.

Exploring these new possibilities in music, Carol also started exploring new possibilities in life. According to her mother, at home and at other settings outside the sessions, Carol improved her communication and autonomy. It is easier for the family to understand her and leave her doing an activity alone, when needed, as she is calmer and expresses herself better. She is more open to new things, showing interest for new movies, dances and games. She is more aware of what's going on around her, she asks for things she wants and can wait for them.

Therefore, with this Nordoff-Robbins Music Therapy process, Carol developed, and integrated herself better into the world. Listening to the musical potentials of her laughing, inviting her expressive vocalizations through supportive melodic-harmonic-rhythmic forms, and thus leading her laughing into singing were essential for Carol to engage in shared meaningful musical experiences with the music therapist and benefit from Music Therapy.

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